

Highly-Sensitive Dual-Mode Luminescence Manometer Based on a Novel Organic Complex Material - $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$

Maja Szymczak¹, Marcin Runowski², Dorota Kwiatek³, Szymon Sobczak², Przemysław Woźny²,
Maciej Kubicki², Grzegorz Dutkiewicz², Andrzej Katrusiak², Lukasz Marciniak¹

¹ Institute of Low Temperature and Structure Research, Polish Academy of Sciences, Okólna 2, 50-422 Wrocław, Poland

² Adam Mickiewicz University, Faculty of Chemistry, Uniwersytetu Poznańskiego 8, 61-614 Poznań, Poland

³ Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry, Polish Academy of Sciences, Z. Noskowskiego 12/14, 61-704 Poznań, Poland

*corresponding authors: runowski@amu.edu.pl (M.R); szymon.sobczak@amu.edu.pl (S.S.)
l.marciniak@intibs.pl (L.M.)

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Abstract

The advancement of ultra-sensitive optical manometers is crucial for exploring the behavior of materials under extreme conditions. Herein we introduce a novel rare-earth complex $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ as a promising candidate for high-precision pressure sensing, addressing the gap in sensitivity of existing luminescent manometers below 1 GPa. Through comprehensive high-pressure spectroscopic and single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies, we have found a phase transition in $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ at 1.25 GPa where the ambient-pressure phase α (space group $Pbcn$) transforms to high-pressure phase β (space group $P2_1/n$). This

process reduces the contribution of intramolecular anagostic bonds complementing the coordination sphere modifying the observed emission spectra, underpinning the role of the crystal-engineering in the development of dual-mode (ratiometric and lifetime-based) luminescence manometers. The ratiometric mode, measuring the intensity ratio between two emission bands of Eu^{3+} ions, demonstrates a remarkable relative sensitivity, exceeding 120.7% GPa^{-1} around 1.6 GPa. The lifetime-based mode utilizes pressure-influenced luminescence kinetics and shows the maximal relative sensitivity of 55.1% GPa^{-1} , classifying it as the most sensitive optical manometer operating in this mode. The unique bimodal readouts and unparalleled sensitivity of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ across both modes significantly advance pressure sensing technologies.

1. Introduction

A comprehensive understanding of the spectroscopic properties of phosphors enables their adept utilization across a wide range of applications.^[1,2] High-pressure spectroscopy emerges as a key tool in deciphering the spectroscopic characteristics of materials, providing insights not only into the local coordination of luminescent ions but also into the mechanical stability of the material and structural changes induced by applied pressure.^[3-8] Beyond crucial information on fundamental science/state of the art, such high-pressure investigations facilitate the development of luminescence-based pressure sensors, which exhibit significant application potential^[9-12]. In this context, there is a great interest in phosphors that undergo substantial structural changes under pressure affecting the spectroscopic properties of the luminescent ion, while maintaining the its crystalline form to ensure repeatability across compression-decompression cycles.^[13-18] Although many materials have been proposed for remote pressure sensing, a majority, primarily inorganic,

demonstrate low sensitivity below 1 GPa. In most cases, this limitation can be attributed to the rigidity of the inorganic framework, which is only slightly affected by the influence of high pressure.^[4,19]

To overcome this limitation, hybrid organic-inorganic materials have been proposed as promising alternatives for developing manometers that operate below 1 GPa. These materials are softer, and thus, pressure has a more pronounced influence on their conformation and crystal environment. In this regard, modifications of the coordination sphere of such materials have an especially strong impact on their emission properties. Recently considerable efforts have focused on the interplay of the less common bonding interactions involving the metals (M) and a C–H bond of the organic ligand fragments in hybrid organic-inorganic materials, owing to their potential implications for optoelectronic properties and the formation of supramolecular synthons.^[20–24] These interactions, typically classified based on geometrical features, are described as either agostic or anagostic interactions.^[25–27] Agostic bonds, formed by electron-deficient early transition metal ions, are characterized by relatively short M···H distances, between 1.8 and 2.3 Å, and M···H–C angles ranging 90 – 140°. Anagostic bonds, show much longer M···H distances with $d \approx 2.3 - 3.4$ Å and $\angle \approx 110 - 170^\circ$ angles.^[28,29] The strain-induced alteration of the coordination sphere through modification of these interactions can lead to the development of a novel class of materials, characterized by increased sensitivity and suitability for low-pressure sensing applications.

Among luminescent ions employed in manometry, such as Cr³⁺, Ce³⁺, Eu²⁺, Sm²⁺, Nd³⁺, Eu³⁺-containing materials are especially suited for pressure sensing due to their distinct spectroscopic properties^[12,17,30–38]. The emission intensity of these materials, originating from the ⁵D₀→⁷F₂ electric-dipole transition, is highly sensitive to Eu³⁺ ions local coordination^[39,40]. This

allows for the development of ratiometric manometers by comparing emission intensities to the stable $^5D_0 \rightarrow ^7F_1$ magnetic dipole transition. Additionally, pressure-induced shifts in Eu^{3+} ions multiplets positions affect non-radiative processes in excited states, altering luminescence kinetics. Therefore, Eu^{3+} -based phosphors are particularly valuable for manometric studies and applications.

In the pursuit of a dual-modal luminescence manometer capable of high-precision sensing below 1 GPa, we have investigated the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ organic complex, noted for its red photoluminescence driven by energy transfer (ET) from organic ligands to Eu^{3+} ions and possible changes of structural conformation. High-pressure X-ray diffraction studies have revealed a phase transition at 1.25 GPa. This finding has facilitated creation of a luminescence manometer with dual readout capabilities: a ratiometric mode based on luminescence intensity ratio (LIR) and another based on luminescence kinetics. The $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ manometer exhibits a significant sensitivity in both modes, with the relative sensitivity of 120.7 % GPa^{-1} in the ratiometric mode and 55.1 % GPa^{-1} in the kinetics-based mode. The combination of these modalities, along with the observed sensitivity magnitude, positions this organic complex as a viable-option promising material for optical pressure sensing in extreme conditions.

2. Experimental Section

Materials

All reagents necessary for the synthesis of the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ were used without prior purification: europium (III) nitrate hexahydrate $\text{Eu}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.999% p.a.; Sigma-Aldrich); 2,2'-bipyridine N,N'-dioxide, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ (98% of purity; Sigma-Aldrich); methyl alcohol, MtOH (99.8% p.a.; POCH); and ammonium hexafluorophosphate, NH_4PF_6 (95%; Sigma-Aldrich).

Synthesis

The 0.5 mmol of the $\text{Eu}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in a 20 cm^3 mixture of water and methanol ($V_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}:V_{\text{MeOH}}/1:9$) at 50°C . A solution of 2,2'-bipyridine N,N'-dioxide (1 mmol) in 10 cm^3 of water-methanol mixture ($V_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}:V_{\text{MeOH}}/1:1$) was added to the previously prepared solution of europium (III) nitrate with constant stirring. After 20 minutes, 10 cm^3 of a 0.15 M solution of NH_4PF_6 in water-methanol mixture ($V_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}:V_{\text{MeOH}}/1:1$) was added dropwise. The solution was stirred for 3 hours at 50°C , and then the resulting precipitate was removed, leaving behind a clear solution from which the colourless crystals of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ were crystallized.

Methods

IR spectra were recorded using an FT-IR spectrophotometer, JASCO 4200, in a transmission mode. Excitation and emission spectra at ambient conditions were measured using a Hitachi F-7000 spectrofluorometer. The emission spectra and luminescence decay curves under high-pressure conditions were collected with a QuantaMasterTM 40 spectrophotometer equipped with an Opolette 355LD UVDM tunable laser (optical parametric oscillator – OPO), with a repetition rate of 20 Hz, as an excitation source and a Hamamatsu R928 photomultiplier as a detector. All spectra were appropriately corrected for the instrumental response.

Single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies at high-pressure

For the high-pressure X-ray diffraction studies of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$, single crystals were mounted in a modified Merrill–Bassett diamond anvil cell^[41], with the anvils directly mounted on steel backing plates. The gasket was made of a 0.3 mm thick steel foil with spark-eroded holes of ≈ 0.4 mm in diameter. Pressure calibration was achieved using the ruby fluorescence method with a Photon Control spectrometer, ensuring an accuracy of 0.02 GPa^[42,43]. Single-crystal X-ray diffraction data were collected up to 4.20 GPa using a four-circle diffractometer equipped with a

CCD detector and a Mo K α X-ray source ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The DAC was centred using the gasket-shadowing method^[44]. CrysAlisPro software (version 1.171.40.53a; Rigaku Corporation: Wroclaw, Poland, 2019) was used for the data collection and processing. For refining the structure of α -Eu(bpyO₂)₄(PF₆)₃ at high pressure, the ambient-pressure structure was used as the starting model for the lowest of high-pressure data sets, and then consecutively the refined model was used for the next higher-pressure point. The structure of phase β was solved with direct methods using Shelxs and refined with Shelxl^[45] using the Olex2^[45,46] suite. Hydrogen atoms were located from molecular geometry and integrated into the structural model with isotropic temperature factors. Structural drawings were prepared using Mercury CSD 4.0^[47] software, and all high-pressure CIFs have been submitted to the CCDC with numbers 2346017- 2346025. The structure at room conditions was measured using an Oxford Supernova diffractometer equipped with graphite-monochromated Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$) and was deposited to the CCDC with number 2345591. The detailed crystallographic information are presented in Tables S1 and S2 in Supporting Information

3. Results and discussion

At ambient conditions, Eu(bpyO₂)₄(PF₆)₃ crystallizes in the orthorhombic system with space group *Pbcn*, further denoted as α -phase. The asymmetric part of the unit cell contains half of the complex molecule and 1.5 hexafluorophosphate anions ($Z/Z' = 4/0.5$). The Eu³⁺ cation is coordinated by eight oxygen atoms of four bpyO₂ ligands (Figure 1a). The structure of α -phase is porous, with the free volume, calculated with the program Mercury^[48] for probe radius 1.0 \AA and grid spacing 0.1 \AA , of 174 \AA^3 at room conditions. The basic characterization of the complex studied was supported by the FT-IR analysis, as shown in the SI file (Figure S1).

Figure 1. a) The $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4^{3+}$ molecule; b-c) pressure-induced changes in b) the unit-cell volume and c) unit-cell parameters as for phases α and β .

The coordination polyhedron of this complex molecule can be characterized as an intermediate form between a square antiprism and a dodecahedron, similar to the previously described $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ ^[49]. Interestingly, the coordination sphere of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ is additionally complemented by two, related by the 2-fold axis, anagostic contacts with $d(\text{H}\cdots\text{Eu})$ distances equal to 3.608(2) Å and with angles $\angle(\text{C}-\text{H}\cdots\text{Eu}) = 147.09(1)^\circ$. The anagostic bonds, frequently associated with the catalytic properties of organometallic compounds,^[26] in $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ lead to the formation of the two-dimensional intramolecular aggregate of the complexes located at (101) crystallographic plane. The volume compression, β_v , of phase α up to 1.10 GPa progresses monotonically and the average compressibility calculated as $\beta_v = -1/V \partial V/\partial p$ is 0.089(5) GPa^{-1} . The linear compressibility along the [x] and [z] directions exhibit a non-linear behaviour (Figure 1c and Table 1), which coincidence with the direction of anagostic interaction consisting on the intramolecular aggregate. Initially, in the range between 0.1 MPa and 0.8 GPa, the material is strongly compressed with the linear compressibility along crystal directions [100] and [001] defined as $\beta_a = -1/a \partial a/\partial p$ and $\beta_c = -1/c \partial c/\partial p$, equal to 0.05(3) GPa^{-1} and 0.04(3) GPa^{-1} , respectively. Above 0.8 GPa, β_c significantly increases and at 1.10 GPa $\beta_c = 0.072(3) \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ and

along crystal direction a small negative linear compressibility with β_a equal to $-0.01(8) \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ appears. These unconventional changes lead to the convex shape of the compression function of a and c (Figure 1c) in phase α may originate from the character the agnostic interactions and ligands conformations.^[50] The bpyO ligands are rigid with only one possible rotation axis allowing for twisting of the 1-dioxide pyridine rings. Thus the bpyO conformation can be described by a N1-C5-C6-N2 torsion angle τ_A and τ_B respectively for two independent ligand molecules present in phase α (Figure S2 in Supporting Information). Above 0.8 GPa the ligands become more planar when the τ_A and τ_B drop by more than 10° .

The compression above 1.25 GPa leads to an abrupt volume drop of about 100 \AA^3 (Figure 1b) marking a first-order phase transition. This pressure-induced ferroelastic transformation to phase β , of the monoclinic $P2_1/n$ space group, with the Aizu notation of $mmmF2/m$ symbol can be representing the group-subgroup relation. The symmetry of phase α , of orthorhombic space group $Pbcn$, is reduced to the monoclinic $P112_1/n$ in phase β . In this study we have presented phase β in the conventional monoclinic setting of space group $P12_1/n1$, after exchanging directions [y] and [x] according to the following matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_\alpha \\ b_\alpha \\ c_\alpha \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_\beta \\ b_\beta \\ c_\beta \end{pmatrix}.$$

In the phase β , the asymmetric part of the unit-cell increases ($Z/Z' = 4/1$) and contains whole $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ molecule and three PF_6^- anions. During the phase transition the PF_6^- anions shift and rotate while the coordination sphere of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4$ is preserved. The magnitude of PF_6^- displacement correlates to the elongation of the [001] direction (corresponding to the [010] direction in phase α) and again leads to arise of some small void content (of around 18.6 \AA^3 at 1.33 GPa).

Table 1. Selected crystallographic data of α and β phases of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$.

Phase	α	α	α	β	β
Pressure (GPa)	0.001	0.88	1.10	1.33	4.20
Space group	<i>Pbcn</i>	<i>Pbcn</i>	<i>Pbcn</i>	<i>P2₁/n</i>	<i>P2₁/n</i>
Unit-cell: <i>a</i> (Å)	13.3593(4)	12.752(19)	12.7784(19)	12.677(8)	12.4021(7)
<i>b</i> (Å)	24.6393(6)	24.441(5)	24.42(7)	13.5809(9)	12.6985(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	14.9397(3)	14.444(3)	14.216(2)	25.002(2)	24.740(19)
β (°)	90	90	90	90.42(2)	90.772(14)
Volume (Å ³)	4917.61(2)	4501.79	4437(13)	4304(3)	3896(3)
<i>Z</i> / <i>Z'</i>	4/0.5	4/0.5	4/0.5	4/1	4/1
<i>D_x</i> (g/cm ³)	1.809	1.976	2.005	2.067	2.282

The reduction of the complex symmetry in phase β releases the C—H \cdots Eu anagostic bonds and allows them to differentiate. Thus, in phase β , only one anagostic bond to the metallic centre is preserved (Figure 2), changing the complexes aggregation motif to the zigzag chains bonded by the intermolecular anagostic interactions extending along [010] crystal direction. The further compression leads to a significant reduction of the C—H \cdots Eu distance, which reduces from 3.355(3) Å at 1.33 GPa to 3.014(4)Å at 4.20 GPa confirming the attractive character of this interaction.

Figure 2. The C—H...Eu distances (black squares) and anagostic bond angle (red squares) plotted as a function of pressure, the C—H bond distance was normalized to 1.089 Å. On the left, the Eu-coordination sphere complemented by the anagostic interactions in phases α and β , the PF_6^- anions were omitted for clarity.

The recorded excitation spectra (Figure 3a), obtained by monitoring a $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 610 \text{ nm}$ at ambient conditions, are dominated by a broad band which is a superposition of the charge transfer band (CTB) associated with an electron transfer from the filled 2p orbital of O^{2-} ligand to the partially filled 4f orbital of the Eu^{3+} ion and the ligand absorption band. The maximum of this band is located at approximately at 328 nm. Additionally, the narrow and less intense bands related to the forbidden intra-configurational 4f-4f transitions of the Eu^{3+} ions can be observed in the

excitation spectrum. These lines correspond to electron transition from ground state 7F_0 to excited states 5D_4 , 5L_7 , 5L_6 and 5D_3 , with the maxima at around 361, 381, 395, and 416 nm, respectively.

In the emission spectrum obtained upon excitation at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 343$ nm, the bands related to depopulated excited states 5D_0 and 5D_1 of Eu^{3+} were observed. Specifically, bands with a maximum at approximately 592, 613, 657, and 705 nm were recorded, representing the electronic transitions from the 5D_0 excited state to the 7F_1 , 7F_2 , 7F_3 and 7F_4 ground states of Eu^{3+} ions, respectively. In Figure 3b, there is also a magnification of the spectral range from around 525-560 nm, revealing low-intensity bands associated with the $^5D_1 \rightarrow ^7F_0$, $^5D_1 \rightarrow ^7F_1$ and $^5D_1 \rightarrow ^7F_2$ electronic transitions of Eu^{3+} , with the maximum at approximately 524, 547, and 587 nm, respectively. The domination of the $^5D_0 \rightarrow ^7F_2$ electronic dipole transition band^[51,52] according to the Judd-Ofelt theory suggest, that the Eu^{3+} ions in $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ are located in a non-centrosymmetric crystallographic sites, which is also corroborated by our structural investigations.

Figure 3. a) Excitation spectrum (recorded at $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 610$ nm); b) emission spectrum ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 343$ nm) with magnification of the spectral range with bands associated with $^5D_1 \rightarrow ^7F_j$ electronic transitions of Eu^{3+} in $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ recorded at ambient conditions.

To evaluate the suitability of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ for pressure sensing, its emission spectra were recorded as a function of pressure in the compression-decompression cycle (Figures 4a, S3 and S4). The pressure-dependent studies were conducted at room temperature in a diamond anvil cell, in a pressure range of 0.11 - 5.02 GPa, upon an excitation wavelength of 343 nm. The obtained pressure-dependent emission spectra were normalized and depicted in Figure 4a. The emission spectrum at 0.11 GPa exhibited an intense and sharp emission band associated with the ${}^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow {}^7\text{F}_2$ electronic dipole transition of Eu^{3+} , along with less intense emission bands corresponding to electron transitions between the excited ${}^5\text{D}_0$ state and ground states ${}^7\text{F}_0$, ${}^7\text{F}_1$, ${}^7\text{F}_3$, and ${}^7\text{F}_4$ of Eu^{3+} . To gain deeper insight into the effect of applied hydrostatic pressure on the spectroscopic properties of Eu^{3+} ions in $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$, the normalized low- and high-pressure emission bands associated with the ${}^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow {}^7\text{F}_2$ electronic transition of Eu^{3+} were demonstrated in Figure 4b. As mentioned previously, this band is highly sensitive to variations in crystal field (CF) strength, which makes it an excellent structural probe of alterations in the local environment of Eu^{3+} ions. Figure 4c and 3d clearly show significant changes in both the spectral position of the emission band and its full width at half maximum (FWHM) (pressure-dependent maxima of the other bands are in Figure S5). A similar trend is observed for both parameters: initially, up to approximately 0.7 GPa, the only slight changes are observed, but above this value, there is a sharp increase until reaching relative stability at around 2.5 GPa. This rapid increase of the spectroscopic parameters of the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ corresponds to the phase transformation from phase α to the phase β , where only phase β exists above 2.5 GPa. In terms of the peak centroid, the spectral shift from 610.89 nm at 0.11 GPa to approximately 614.85 nm above 2.5 GPa was found. On the other hand, the FWHM changes from 3.04 nm at 0.11 GPa to about 6.90 nm above 2.5 GPa. The changes of both parameters were also investigated during decompression process, when the observed effects were reversible. In the

pressure range between 1 GPa and 2.5 GPa, the hysteresis connected to the phase α -to- β transformation was observed.

Initially, the emission intensity, of the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$ electronic transition of Eu^{3+} , decreases with applied pressure which is a characteristic effect observed in the high-pressure studies resulting from a higher probability of non-radiative depopulation of emitting state attributed to pressure-induced structural defects (Figure 4e). Upon reaching a pressure of approximately 2.5 GPa, a rapid and monotonic increase in emission intensity was observed. At about 5.0 GPa, the achieved emission intensity reached approximately 80% of the value obtained at 0.11 GPa. This pressure-induced increase in emission intensity of Eu^{3+} ions may be attributed to a pressure-induced spectral shift of the excitation band due to the formation of phase β ^[53]. As a consequence of increasing pressure, the spectral overlap between the excitation wavelength and the excitation band of $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ increases.

Another crucial parameter indicating structural changes in the surrounding of the Eu^{3+} ion, is the ratio of the intensities of the bands corresponding to the ratio between ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$ and ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$ transitions. This ratio, also known as the asymmetry ratio (AR), generally reflects the symmetry around the Eu^{3+} ion. For the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$, the AR parameter drastically decreases with increasing pressure (Figure 4f), dropping by approximately 2-fold at a pressure of around 5.0 GPa compared to the value obtained at 0.11 GPa. Despite the overall decrease of the global symmetry of the crystal, caused by the pressure-induced phase transition at around 1.25 GPa (from orthorhombic to monoclinic crystal system), the reduction of the AR parameter indicates an increase in the local symmetry around Eu^{3+} ions. Additionally, significant differences in the shape of the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$ emission band can be found with increased pressure, which can be connected to the observed structural changes.

In the terms of structural transformations under high pressure, we can consider two components: (i) the close surrounding of Eu^{3+} including the coordination sphere built of eight oxygen atoms from four bpyO₂ ligands; and (ii) the more distant crystal field that drastically lowers in the symmetry at the phase transition at 1.25 GPa. The convex strain of the linear compressibility of parameter c (Fig. 1c) connected to the phase transition that lowers the crystal symmetry involves breaking of the anagostic bond $\text{CH}\cdots\text{Eu}$. This frustrate the relaxed electronic structure of the central metal cation dumping the observed emission spectrum. On increasing the pressure, the ligands gradually fill up the gaps in the coordination sphere, again leading to increase of the emission. The two opposite processes, frustrating the crystal field around Eu^{3+} and flattering of the complex geometry strongly contributes to observed changes of the AR parameter.

Figure 4. a) Pressure-dependent emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 343 \text{ nm}$); b) comparison of the normalized low and high-pressure emission spectra; c) peak centroid, d) FWHM and e) normalized emission intensity of the band associated with the ${}^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow {}^7\text{F}_2$ electronic transition of Eu^{3+} as a function of applied hydrostatic pressure (full dots correspond to the

compression, and empty dots correspond to the decompression); f) pressure-dependent intensity ratio of the emission bands AR associated with the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$ and ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$ electronic transitions of Eu^{3+} in $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$.

The significant pressure-induced changes in the complex structure $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ allow to apply a ratiometric approach for pressure sensing. Therefore, four readout modes (LIR_{1-4}) were introduced as follows (see Figure 5a):

$$\text{LIR}_1 = \frac{\int_{600nm}^{700nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4) d\lambda}{\int_{587nm}^{683nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1) d\lambda} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{LIR}_2 = \frac{\int_{587nm}^{600nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1) d\lambda}{\int_{606nm}^{611nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2) d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{LIR}_3 = \frac{\int_{683nm}^{700nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4) d\lambda}{\int_{606nm}^{611nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2) d\lambda} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{LIR}_4 = \frac{\int_{611.5nm}^{623nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2) d\lambda}{\int_{606nm} I(\text{Eu}^{3+} : {}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2) d\lambda} \quad (4)$$

The pressure-dependent LIR_{1-4} depicted in Figure 5b reveals a sharp increase in value between pressure of approximately 0.8 GPa and 3 GPa was observed. The most significant, 10-fold, enhancement was observed for the LIR_3 within the aforementioned pressure range. Once reaching pressure around 3 GPa, the LIR values reached the plateau and further increase in pressure does not affect their values. The observed sharp increase in LIR above 0.8 GPa results from the

phase transformation of the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$. The quantitative analysis of the pressure-induced changes in the emission spectra of the phosphor was performed by the calculation of the relative sensitivities S_{R_x} were determined using the following equation Eq. (5):

$$S_{R_x} = \frac{1}{LIR_x} \frac{\Delta LIR_x}{\Delta p} 100\% \quad (5)$$

where ΔLIR represents the change of the LIR parameter in response to the pressure change Δp and $x = 1, 2, 3, 4$ corresponding to LIR_1, LIR_2, LIR_3 and LIR_4 , respectively. The pressure-dependent relative sensitivities for all readout modes are presented in Figure 5c. The highest sensitivity was achieved for the LIR_3 mode, reaching $120.7\% \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ at 1.62 GPa. For LIR 1, 2, and 4, the $S_{R_{\max}}$ was $53.92\% \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ (0.97 GPa), $72.79\% \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ (1.11 GPa), and $107.37\% \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ (0.86 GPa), respectively. These obtained values demonstrate that by appropriately defining the LIR parameter, the sensor parameters can be adjusted to shift the maximal relative sensitivity according to the desired operating pressure range (see Figure 5d).

Figure 5. a) Pressure-dependent normalized integral intensities of four different spectral ranges of emission spectra used in the LIR_x calculations; b) normalized LIR_x values and c) corresponding S_{R_x} as a function of applied hydrostatic pressure; d) dependence of $S_{R_x,max}$ on applied pressure for the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$.

The change in the local ion's symmetry affects not only the shape of the emission spectra but the probabilities of the depopulation of the emitting state. Therefore, the observed structural changes in the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ complex associated with the applied pressure should influence on the luminescence kinetics of the $^5\text{D}_0$ state of Eu^{3+} ions. To verify this hypothesis, the luminescence decay profiles of the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ using the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_2$ electronic transition of Eu^{3+} ions were measured, both during compression and decompression (see Figures 6a and S6). As shown in Figure 6a, at ambient pressure almost a single exponential profile can be observed. However, as the pressure increases, their shape starts to deviate from the single-exponential. Therefore, in order

to perform a quantitative analysis in a reliable conditions the measured decay profiles were fitted using bi-exponential cure (6) and the average lifetimes (τ_{avr}) of the 5D_0 excited state of Eu^{3+} were determined, using Eq. (7):

$$y = y_0 + A_1 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{x}{t_1}\right) + A_2 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{x}{t_2}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{avr} = \frac{A_1 \tau_1^2 + A_2 \tau_2^2}{A_1 \tau_1 + A_2 \tau_2} \quad (7)$$

where, τ_1 and τ_2 represent the two luminescence decay time components, and A_1 and A_2 are the corresponding amplitudes. Based on the decay curves, the calculated average lifetime of the 5D_0 excited state of Eu^{3+} shortens with increasing applied pressure, from $\approx 379 \mu s$ at 0.11 GPa to about 270 μs at about 1.5 GPa. After reaching 1.5 GPa, the τ_{avr} remains unchanged until about 3 GPa. Above that threshold a further shortening of the average lifetimes to about 211 μs at 5 GPa was observed. The observed shortening is attributed to the pressure induced increase in the probability of the nonradiative depopulation of the 5D_0 state. The observed variations of the τ_{avr} correlates with the pressure range associated with the onset of phase transformation, as indicated by XRD studies, spanning from approximately 0.8 to 3 GPa. This range also aligns with the spectral changes in the bandwidth and centroid of band associated with $^5D_0 \rightarrow ^7F_2$ electronic transition of Eu^{3+} ions.

The relative sensitivity of the lifetime-based manometric approach was determined with Eq. (8) by the analogy to the Eq. (5):

$$S_R = \frac{1}{\tau_{avr}} \frac{\Delta \tau_{avr}}{\Delta p} 100\% \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta\tau_{avr}$ represents the change in τ_{avr} with a change in pressure of Δp . The $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ luminescent manometer exhibits the highest relative sensitivity S_R to pressure changes at ambient pressure, reaching a sensitivity of $55.1\% \text{ GPa}^{-1}$. The sensitivity gradually decreases up to about 1.8 GPa and then increases again, reaching $15.0\% \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ at approximately 4 GPa. Beyond this pressure value, a decrease of S_R was once more observed.

Figure 6. Pressure-dependent luminescence decay curves ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 343 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 610 \text{ nm}$) -a); determined average luminescence lifetimes of $^5\text{D}_0$ state of Eu^{3+} obtained during compression (filled symbols) and decompression (empty symbols) -b) and corresponding S_R -c) as a function of pressure for the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$.

Up to date, only a few luminescence manometers based on ratiometric or luminescence kinetics-based modes have been proposed. Figure 7a and 7b below provide a summary of the most sensitive reported luminescence manometers based on aforementioned pressure readout modes. As shown, the obtained relative sensitivities are very high, especially in the kinetics-mode, classifying the developed sensor as the most sensitive manometer based on luminescence decay times, and a second most-sensitive gauge operating in ratiometric mode, reported so far. In addition, it is worth noting that in the case of inorganic pressure gauges, high sensitivities are usually observable for pressures above 1 GPa. From this perspective, a sensitivity of $S_R=115\% \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ around 0.8 GPa for

LIR₁ and S_R=120% GPa⁻¹ at 1.6 GPa (LIR₃) are particularly beneficial for applications. It is worth mentioning that, currently, this is the most sensitive luminescence manometer based on narrow emission bands of lanthanide ions, both in the ratiometric and luminescence kinetics-based modes. The obtained sensitivity values highlight the promising potential of using phosphors exhibiting pressure-induced phase transitions in highly-sensitive luminescence manometry.

Figure 7. a-b) Comparison of the luminescent manometers emitting in the visible spectral range based on LIR (a) and average lifetime of excited state (b) modes.^[14,31,54–58]

3. Conclusions

Here we demonstrate the remarkable potential of high-pressure techniques for probing material behavior under extreme conditions, by developing a completely new optical pressure sensor, currently being the most sensitive manometer operating in kinetics-mode, and allowing accurate multi-modal visual pressure readouts. These investigations can shed light on the composition of

planetary interiors and even lead to the discovery of novel materials with unconventional properties. In this context, the development of ultra-sensitive optical pressure sensors holds tremendous significance. Luminescent manometers have garnered significant interest for pressure sensing applications. However, a major hurdle lies in the inherently low sensitivity of most inorganic materials below 1 GPa, primarily due to their limited structural response to pressure variations. This study presents a unique solution by exploring $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$, a recently discovered organic complex, as a pressure sensor material. By employing high-pressure spectroscopic and single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies, we were able to identify a pressure-induced phase transition in the $\text{Eu}(\text{bpyO}_2)_4(\text{PF}_6)_3$ complex at around 1.25 GPa, where the orthorhombic phase α transforms to monoclinic phase β . The transition at 1.25 GPa can be connected with the remarkable anomaly in the emission spectrum as a function of pressure: the normalized integration intensity initially decreases till about 2.6 GPa after which it sharply increases to 5.0 GPa at least; in the decompression run the dip is shifted to a lower pressure around the transition (Figure 4d). The pressure-induced structural rearrangement induces the strain affecting the crystal field around the Eu^{3+} cations. This strain is clearly observed in the unusual convex linear compression along $[z]_\alpha$ of the crystal in phase α . Such a convex strain heralds a phase transition leading to the lowered symmetry of the complex and the coordination sphere in phase β by breaking one of the $\text{CH}\cdots\text{Eu}$ anagostic bond. Observed effects are foundation for the development of a new generation of highly sensitive luminescence manometer with dual readout modes. The manometer offers two operational modes: ratiometric and lifetime-based. The ratiometric mode, which analyzes the intensity ratio between two Eu^{3+} emission bands, achieves an outstanding relative sensitivity exceeding 120% GPa^{-1} at approximately 1.6 GPa. In contrast, the lifetime-based mode, which capitalizes on pressure-dependent luminescence kinetics via the average lifetime of the Eu^{3+} excited state, delivers a maximum relative sensitivity of more than

55% GPa⁻¹ at ambient pressure. The exceptional sensitivity and the availability of two independent readout modes make Eu(bpyO₂)₄(PF₆)₃ a highly promising candidate for pressure sensing applications, particularly in harsh environments where conventional sensors may struggle.

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